

Article

Professor Aniebiet Inyang Ntui

2 h · Climate Advocate

Splitting Continent: Climate Change and the East African Rift System

The African continent is gradually splitting into two, a geological process that has been ongoing for millions of years. However, recent studies suggest that climate change may be exacerbating this process, leading to more frequent and intense geological activity. The consequences of this activity could be devastating for the people and wildlife of East Africa, where the East African Rift System is located.

The African continent is made up of several tectonic plates, including the Somali, Nubian, and Arabian plates. The Somali and Nubian plates are slowly disintegrating from each other, while the Arabian plate continues to pull away. This gradual process will eventually split the continent into

two sub-continents, creating a new ocean basin between them. The continental rift will happen along the East African Rift Valley, a geologically active region whose formation millions of years ago is similar to that of the tectonic movements that happen at the bottom of oceans.

This geological process has been ongoing for millions of years and is driven by tectonic forces. Nevertheless, recent studies suggest that climate change may be exacerbating this process. As global temperatures rise, the ice caps in Greenland and Antarctica are melting at an alarming rate. This melting ice is causing a significant shift in the weight distribution of the Earth's crust, which in turn is putting pressure on the East African Rift System.

According to a study published in an environmental journal, "The melting of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets is contributing to sea-level rise, but it is also causing a redistribution of mass on the Earth's surface that affects the Earth's rotation and gravitational field." This redistribution of mass is causing changes in the Earth's crustal stress, which can affect the formation of rift valleys.

In addition to the weight distribution shift, climate change is also causing an increase in rainfall and flooding in the region. This increased rainfall is causing erosion, which is further weakening the Earth's crust in the area. As a result, the rift valley is widening, and the risk of earthquakes and volcanic activity is increasing. According to a study published in *Quaternary Science Reviews*, "The interplay of tectonics, erosion, sedimentation, and climate is highly dynamic, and all of these

factors have to be considered to understand the evolution of the East African Rift System."

The impact of climate change on the East African Rift System is complex and multifaceted. Dr Cynthia Ebinger, a renowned American Geoscientist at Tulane University and Professor of Earth and Environmental Sciences at the University of Rochester, has been studying the East African Rift System for over 30 years. She says, "The East African Rift System is a fascinating place to study because it is an active tectonic environment where we can see the formation of new land in real time. However, the impact of climate change on this system is concerning because it is leading to more frequent and intense geological activity, which could have devastating consequences for the people and wildlife of East Africa."

AFRICA SPLITS

Six landlocked countries to get beaches as continent 'splitting into two' – but there's a big downside for tourists

The consequences of this geological activity could be devastating for the people and wildlife of East Africa. The region is home to some of the world's most iconic wildlife, including elephants, lions, and giraffes. From statistics by the East African Community (EAC), It is home to some 40% of the continent's mammal species (402 species), a huge diversity of birds (1,061 species), reptiles and amphibians (293 species), and higher plants (5,793 species). It is also home to millions of people who depend on the land for their livelihoods. Increased geological activity could lead to displacement, crop failures, and loss of life.

To mitigate the potential impacts of the East African Rift System's geological activity, it is essential to continue monitoring the region's geological and climate conditions closely. Additionally, it is critical to implement measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and limit the extent of climate change.

By working together, we can help to ensure that the East African Rift System remains a fascinating place to study and admire, without causing harm to the people and wildlife that call it home.